

Potential of In-pipe Micro-Hydropower Systems for Power Generation in Makueni County Kenya

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Abstract:- Literature shows that only 56% of Kenyan households had access to electricity, with rural areas having the lowest access rate at 31%. The high cost of extending the power grid to remote areas and power losses on distribution are significant challenges facing rural electrification. In addressing power accessibility problems especially in the rural areas, there is a need for tap hydropower generation through invention and implementation of in-duct turbines to maximize the utilization of already existing pressurised water ducts that supply water in various parts of Kenya for hydropower generation. This work focuses on identifying and mapping possible Micro Hydropower Schemes for hydropower generation in Makueni County located in Eastern Kenya. The County is supplied by four gravity fed water ducts with slopes ranging from 40m to 800m and from 14m to 183m. In this study we focussed mainly on duct sections with gradients ranging from 14m to 183m located in Kweleli and Manooni in Nzau Sub-County, and Ikokani and Mulima in Mbooni West Sub-County with pipe sizes ranging from 50mm to 200mm because they offer a significant potential for construction of pico/micro hydropower generation systems.

Potential micro hydropower (MHP) sites were identified, evaluated, and mapped using the Open Data Kit (ODK) approach and GPS mapping. The gradients and heights/heads of possible locations along the smaller gravity ducts were determined by measuring/picking the point heights above sea level of the pipeline slope start and slope using GPS and collecting hydraulic head data along the county's the major selected water supply ducts. The maps were generated using a quantum geographical information system (QGIS). The prospective MHP locations varied in several ways, including particular power estimates ranging from 0.59 to 23.63 kilowatts. According to the analysis, there are 33 viable sites along the four water projects. Thirteen possible MHP locations were found along Manooni, nine along Mulima, eight along Ikokani, and three along the Kweleli water schemes pipeline. Using an efficiency value of 0.7, six (6) viable MHP locations with power ranges of 15 to 25KW were identified. Two (2) possible MHP sites had power ranges of 10 to 15KW, five (5) prospective MHP sites had power ranges of 5 to 10KW, nineteen (19) potential MHP sites had power ranges of 1 to 5KW, and only one (97%) potential MHP site had a power range of 1 to 5KW.

On the basis of these findings, it can be concluded that excess energy (pressure energy) from the flowing water inside pipelines can be extracted to meet electric power demand for rural communities in Makueni County, Kenya. It is clear from our research finding, that there is significant power/energy can be harvested from the pipelines in different operating conditions/applications. Thus, the micro-hydropower systems are really promising alternative technology for power generation especially in rural areas of Kenya and other countries.

Keywords:- Break pressure tank (BPT), Duct, Hydropower, Modeling, Renewable Energy, Small Hydropower Schemes, Valve, GPS and quantum geographical information system (QGIS).

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydropower is a mature and cost-competitive renewable energy technology that plays a strategic critical position in the electricity mix of the twenty-first century, accounting for more than 16% of global electricity output and around 85% of global renewable electricity. Literature review shows that hydropower capacity has been increasing steadily in the world and over 160 nations depend on hydropower for socio-economic development. Hydroelectricity offers various benefits over other electrical power sources, including high dependability, established technology, great efficiency (about 90% efficiency), very cheap operating and maintenance costs, flexibility, and substantial storage capacity [Gokhale, et al. 2017]. Furthermore, given the instability of other renewable energy supplies such as wind and solar, hydropower systems can aid in moderating oscillations between demand and supply. This is possible because to the wide range of hydropower plant sizes.

In this study, we investigated the potential of hydropower electric power generation from water flowing through pipes, particularly vertical pipelines, which have a lot of kinetic and pressure energies. Inside the pipe, the flow rate is usually constant and the end-user requirement is simply flow rate rather than pressure. As a result, a portion of the pressure energy can be collected and transformed into electrical energy [Miller, 2016]. Several technical methods have been proposed to replace pressure-reducing valves with energy-producing devices, allowing for effective power conversion from reliable water network pressure regulation.

Hydroelectric power is a tried-and tested technology that generates 19% of the world's electricity from both large and small power facilities [Gokhale et al. 2017]. Kenya's electricity generation is liberalized, with hydropower dominating the energy mix [Miller, 2016]. With the implementation of the feed-in tariff (FIT) policy in 2008, small-scale candidate sites are likely to emerge and serve well for the delivery of power to communities, small companies, or farms [Makueni County Government, 2018]. Aside from the few big and medium hydropower schemes functioning in Kenya, others include (i) small (10-1 MW), (ii) Mini (1MW - 100 kW), (iii) micro (100kW - 5 kW), and pico (5 kW) hydropower [Shrestha,et al. 2021].

A. Micro Hydropower Potential

A micro hydropower plant (MHP) is a renewable energy source that is created by falling water through an open or closed waterway that drives a turbine coupled to an electric generator. MHP is regarded to be an appropriate renewable energy source for homes, ranches, and remote villages. MHP technology is the most mature of the renewable energy power plant technologies, with better efficiency (70-90%) than wind, wave, and solar power plants. MHP electricity can be utilized for a variety of purposes. MHP can continually generate electricity and be connected directly to the load without the need for an energy storage system with the right system planning and design. Applying a variable speed mechanism can increase MHP efficiency and stability of power networks [Bilgili et al. 2018]

B. Study Area

The study area is Makueni County, which borders Kajiado County to the west, Taita Taveta County to the south, Kitui County to the east, and Machakos County to the north. It is located in the dry and semi-arid zones of Kenya's Eastern region, between Latitude 1o 35' and 3o 00' South and Longitude 37o10' and 38o 30' East. Rural areas and the majority of Makueni County are already marked by a shortage of power [Makueni County Government, 2018].

[Show the map of the study area]

According to Makueni County Government, the county is endowed with community water supply systems running to settlement areas from the Volcanic Chyulu, Mbooni, Nzaui, and Kilungu hills, which when developed would aid in reducing energy deficit in rural areas by reaping green energy from small diameter (100mm to 200mm) community gravity water ducts [Makueni County Government, 2018]. This would help with water pressure management by reducing pipeline ruptures and the associated repair expenses as well as disruptions in water supply to customers [Berardi and Giustolisi, 2021]. Furthermore, the construction of such MHPs in the local communities would increase awareness of the benefits associated with the use of renewable energy technologies (RETs) in Makueni County's power matrix, particularly through the harvesting of hydropower from small gravity water ducts.

A reconnaissance assessment and analysis of the Makueni Water pipeline profiles clearly shows that possible places along the gravity pipelines where Micro hydropower schemes (MHPS) could be created to generate green hydro

energy to supplement the County's energy sources exist. Water pipelines in rural areas and community water delivery systems range in diameter from fifty millimetres (50mm) to two hundred and fifty millimetres (250mm). Water pipeline profiles in Makueni County design Office show the existence of such pipeline trunks extending down from various hills to low places.

C. Objectives

The objective of this study was to identify and map prospective MHP sites along gravity community ducts that transport water in rural regions of Makueni County.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology as shown in Figure 1 was carried out in three stages: data collecting, data processing, and data analysis. During the first phase, data collection questionnaire was designed to obtain the key data viz. the site name, date of data collection, the GPS data for all the potential sites for installation of MHP systems. Other data collected include key features of water pipe intakes, pipeline gradients, streams, rivers, storage tanks, BPTs, washouts and valves. The identification and mapping of the potential MHP sites was done through application of ODK as shown in Figure 1.

A. Site Selection

Makueni County was selected as a case study area because it is presumed to have a good micro hydropower potential for in duct electric power generation.

B. Data collection in stage 1

Stage one data collection included topographic maps, remote sensing data, and field measurement via GPS. In order to determine the hydro power potential, water flow rate at a given time and slope/elevation head (H) was measured. The flow of water (Q) was calculated by amount of water in collected in a container divided by time (t) taken to fill the container [7]. The potential power generated from the micro hydro power scheme was calculated from the information gathered through the site survey [8]. The actual power generated from the given source of water is given by;

$$P = \rho \cdot g \cdot H \cdot Q \cdot \eta \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

Where P = electrical or mechanical power produced in Watts (W), ρ = density of water (kg/m³), g = acceleration due to gravity (m/s²), H = elevation head of water (m), Q = flow rate of water (m³/s), η = overall efficiency of MHPS [9].

The gradients and heights/heads of possible locations along the smaller gravity ducts were determined by measuring/picking the point heights above sea level of and pipeline slope start and slope using GPS and collecting hydraulic head data along the county's principal selected water supply ducts. The maps were created using a quantum geographical information system (QGIS).

The researcher used the Open Data Kit (ODK) process to collect data and GPS to map major pipeline locations to identify and map possible MHP sites. The Open Data Kit (ODK) is an open software which is expandable for gathering,

managing, and utilising data. ODK is an open-source collection of tools developed to build information services for developing regions [10]. A data collection form/questionnaire was first designed in Microsoft word format for all the key data which was to be collected. Such data were; the site name, date of collection, main feature around i.e. storage tanks, BPTs, and the GPS points for all the potential sites and key features including intakes, pipeline slope starts, slope ends, streams, rivers, storage tanks, BPTs, washouts and valves among others. Map production was done in a quantum geographical information system (QGIS) environment. The data was analyzed and overlaid with administrative boundaries to produce the maps for the water pipelines and potential micro hydropower sites. The Open Data Kit (ODK) process was used in the research to carry out data collection and mapping of key pipeline points as diagrammatically summarised in figure 2.

The gravity water schemes subjected to the study were: Kweleli, and Manooni, in Nzauzi Sub-County, Ikokani and Mulima in Mbooni West Sub-County and had pipe diameters ranging from 50mm to 200mm hence had high potential for development of micro hydropower Schemes. An assessment was undertaken using Open Data Kit (ODK) fed data collection form/questionnaire while analysis was done using excel sheets. Using mobile phones, geographical information system (GIS), and global positioning system (GPS) mappers, coordinates of all the intakes, pipelines sections, water storage tanks, break pressure tanks, slopes/gradients, possible MHP Sites were taken. The assessment was undertaken along the water schemes ducts especially where the ducts were in steady slopes and would provide adequate water heads for hydro power production. All the sites along the selected water projects of Manooni, Mulima, Ikokani and Kweleli were mapped as indicated in figures 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively.

C. ODK Process Diagrammatic Summary

Fig. 1: Diagrammatic Representation of Sites Mapping Process

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Our results show that the gravity water schemes had ducts with diameters ranging from 50mm to 200mm, slopes ranging from 40m to 800m while the slopes had sections with gradients varying from 14m to 183m. Further analysis of the section gradients pinpointed to 33 potential of micro hydropower production of power sites and production estimates ranging from 0.59 to 23.63 kilowatts.

As shown in figure 2, out of the 33 identified potential MHP sites, 13 sites were along Manooni, 9 sites along Mulima, 8 sites along Ikokani and 3 sites along Kweleli water scheme pipelines. While applying an efficiency coefficient of 0.7, Six (6) potential MHP sites had a power range of 15 to <25KW, Two (2) potential MHP sites had power range of 10 to <15KW, Five (5) potential MHP with a power range of 5 to <10KW, Nineteen (19) potential sites MHP had a power range of 1 to <5KW while only one (1) potential MHP site power production was in the range of 0 to <1KW.

Fig. 2: Potential MPH Sites Power Ranges

A. Manooni Water Project

The source of water for Manooni water project is rainwater surface runoff harvested through Manooni dam after which water supply is mainly, supplied to consumers using gravity systems. The dam reservoir has a capacity of approximately 0.25 million cubic meters and is in Kilungu (Manooni- Matiliku) hills hence water flows from the hills to distribution lines with sufficient hydraulic heads for possible

development of micro hydroelectric power stations. The flow of water from the intake was found to be 10 litres per Second and the project consisted of the main line of 200mm diameter from the dam to Kitulani ground Masonry tank near kwa Mutula market through Utuneni to Mulala at Kathuma Market and reduces to 75mm diameter at kwa musomi storage tank. The GIS points of all the potential micro hydropower stations are presented in a map as shown in figure 3.

Fig. 3: Manooni Water Project Map

The potential hydropower for various identified Potential sites along Manooni water project pipeline ranged between 2,106W for a head of 22m and 23,632W for a head of 129m. The potential sites and hydropower production levels are presented in figure 4.

Fig. 4: Manooni MHP Sites and Potential Power

B. Mulima Water Project

This project has its intake at Nzeveni in Mbooni hills slopes and its managed by Mbooni Water and Sanitation Company. The source of water is permanent water springs in the forest upstream which feeds Mulima Earth Dam besides harvesting surface runoff during rainfall. The dam has a capacity of 0.1million litres active storage capacity. Water

flows by gravity from dam intake chamber to mavindu storage tank. The flow from the dam is 30 litres per second. The project starts with 225 mm diameter pipe and reduces to 75mm in the lower sides towards Tawa market. The GIS points of all the potential micro hydropower stations along the pipeline are presented in a map as shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5: Mulima Water Project Map

The potential hydropower for various identified sites along Mulima water project pipeline ranged between 2500W for a head of 55m and 19,142W for a head of 85m. The potential sites and hydropower production levels are presented in figure 6.

Fig. 6: Mulima MHP Sites and Potential Power

C. Ikokani Water Project

Ikokani water project is in Mbooni hills and its intake is built across Ikokani River near Nzaini Coffee Factory. The river is recharged upstream at Mutituni and Wathi area by permanent springs which help in stabilizing water flow. The

river flow is 10 litres per second while the flow in the pipe is 2 litres per second. The GIS points of all the potential hydropower stations along the pipeline are presented in a map as shown in figure 7.

Fig. 7: Ikokani Water Project Map

The potential hydropower for various identified sites along Ikokani water project pipeline ranged between 585W for a head of 17m and 4580W for a head of 133m. The potential sites and hydropower production levels are presented in figure 8.

Fig. 8: Ikokani MHP Sites and Potential Power

D. Kweleli Water Project

The Kweleli water project intake is in Nzau hills and the water source is a spring deep inside the Nzau hills forest where water is collected from an intake box using a 100mm diameter pipe which runs for 200m to Ngangani storage Tank. The Ngangani tank to Yiuma market line is 75mm diameter.

The flow from the spring is 3 litres per second and only 1.8 litres per second flows along the pipeline with the rest left for environmental flow. The GIS points of all the potential micro hydropower stations along the pipeline are presented in a map as shown in figure 9.

Fig. 9: Kweleli Water Project Map

The potential hydropower for various identified sites along Kweleli water project pipeline ranged between 2445W for a water head of 71m and 3,891W for a water head of 113m. The potential sites and hydropower production levels are presented in figure 10.

Fig. 10: Kweleli MHP Sites and Potential Power

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The potential micro hydropower (MHP) sites were identified, evaluated, and mapped using the Open Data Kit (ODK) approach and GPS mapping. The gradients and heights/heads of possible locations along the smaller gravity ducts were determined by measuring/picking the point heights above sea level of the pipeline slope start and slope end using GPS and collecting hydraulic head data along the county's major selected water supply ducts. The maps were generated using a quantum geographical information system (QGIS). The prospective MHP locations varied in several ways, including particular power estimates ranging from 0.59 to 23.63 kilowatts. According to the analysis, there are 33 viable sites along the four water projects. Thirteen possible MHP locations were found along Manooni, nine along Mulima, eight along Ikokani, and three along the Kweleli water schemes pipeline. Using an efficiency value of 0.7, six (6) viable MHP locations with power ranges of 15 to 25KW were identified. Two (2) possible MHP sites had power ranges of 10 to 15KW, five (5) prospective MHP sites had power ranges of 5 to 10KW, nineteen (19) potential MHP sites had power ranges of 1 to 5KW, and only one (97%) potential MHP site had a power range of 1 to 5KW. On the basis of these findings, it can be concluded that in-pipe power generation technology in which small water turbines are installed in a water pipe work is one of the most promising energy harvesting systems to meet electric power demand for rural communities in Makueni County in Kenya.

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